

Evaluation of photo degradation efficiency of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs against methylene orange dye under sun light irradiation

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Abstract : The present study has been undertaken to prepare sodium carboxy methyl cellulose (NaCMC) capped ZnO NPs, with multifunctional properties. The NaCMC capped ZnO NPs (0.04 mM and 0.08 mM) were prepared by soft chemical method. The prepared NPs were characterized by XRD, FTIR and SEM-EDS, AFM and UV-Vis absorption studies. It was clear from XRD patterns that NPs were crystallized in hexagonal wurtzite structure with average crystalline size 34 nm to 39 nm. The chemical functional groups in FTIR spectra confirmed the formation of the ZnO NPs. The surface morphology of the samples was explored using SEM micrographs and AFM analysis. The presence of Zn and O was confirmed by EDAX analysis. The optical properties of the samples were examined by UV-Vis absorption analysis. The photo degradation activity of the NPs was investigated against methylene orange dye (MO) under sunlight.

Keywords : Zinc oxide, soft chemical method, photo degradation, sun light methylene orange dye.

Introduction

Nano materials exhibit novel physical, chemical and biological properties. They are multifunctional in nature due to their size¹. The NPs have more surface-to-volume ratio². Zinc oxide is unique and key inorganic material that has attracted extensive research due to its characteristic features and novel applications in wide areas of science and technology. Typically, ZnO is n-type semiconductor which has a wide energy band gap (3.37 eV). It has multiple properties like high piezoelectric constant, high transparency, large electro-optic coefficient, photo catalysis, pyroelectric, bio compatible, antibacterial activity and large exciton binding energy at room temperature³⁻⁶.

The degradation of the untreated effluents is an important process for reducing water pollution in environment. There is a high priority to remove the dyes from industrial effluent before its discharge into surrounding environment. Most of the methods are recently used for

chemical and physical effluent treatment process does not decolorize completely, besides these are high expensive and have more practical difficulties⁸.

The researcher used different synthesize technique like hydrothermal route, sol-gel process, vapor-liquid-solid process, pulsed laser deposition and thermal decomposition for the preparation of zinc oxide NPs with different morphologies^{9,10}. The work has been developed to synthesis zinc oxide NPs with polymer NaCMC capped used to protect the nanocrystals from aggregation. By varying the molar ratio of NaCMC on constant zinc oxide, the phase purity of the product is controlled. Photocatalysis is an important technique used for the decolourization. Semiconductor NPs are mostly used for photocatalytic degradation of toxic organic compound^{11,12}. The present study aimed to prepare NaCMC capped NPs (0.04 mM and 0.08 mM) by soft chemical method. The prepared NPs were characterized by XRD, FT-IR, SEM/EDS, AFM and UV-Vis analysis. The photo degradation efficiency

percentage was also studied for NaCMC capped ZnO NPs (0.04 mM) under sun light irradiation on methylene orange dye (MO).

Materials and method :

Materials :

All chemicals used were of standard AR grade and not further treated. The zinc sulphate heptahydrate ($\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) and sodium carboxy methyl cellulose (NaCMC) were the precursors and double distilled water as a solvent. The methylene orange dye (MO) was used for photo degradation analysis.

Experimental

For synthesis of polymer capped ZnO NPs, 50 ml aqueous solution containing $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 M) and polymer NaCMC (0.04 mM (sample a) and 0.08 mM (sample b)) was mixed with sodium hydroxide (NaOH). The resulting mixture was vigorously stirred for 30 min and then white product was obtained. Further, collected samples were washed with deionized water and dried in air with 80 °C for four hours. The dried powders were further calcinated at 550 °C for two hours.

Photo degradation analysis :

The methylene orange dye solution 30 ml and 20 mg NaCMC capped ZnO NPs were mixed and stirred. The prepared solution was taken in the 100 ml beaker and then placed under sun light irradiation. At five different time intervals (30, 60, 90, 120 and 150 min), 1 ml of the sample was centrifuged to separate the residual catalyst. The each irradiated samples were taken for measuring the absorbance intensity used by UV-absorption measurement to known the decomposition effect.

Results and discussion

Structural analysis (XRD) :

The X-ray diffraction patterns were shown in Fig. 1. All the obtained diffraction peaks were matched with corresponding hexagonal wurtzite structure of ZnO (JCPDS Card No. 36-1451)⁷. The series of characteristic peaks (100), (002), (101), (102), (103), (112) and (200) crystal planes were observed.

The average crystallite size of prepared NPs was calculated using Debye Scherrer equation¹³.

$$D = \frac{0.89 \lambda}{\beta \cos \theta}$$

where, D is the average crystallite size, λ is the incident wave length of X-ray beam, θ is the Bragg's diffraction angle and β is the Full-width at half-maximum intensity. The calculated average particle sizes were 34 nm and 35 nm for sample a and sample b. The influence of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs in bulk heating of the material results in the dipole change of the polar molecules with uniform

Fig. 1. XRD spectra of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs : (a) NaCMC 0.04 mM, (b) NaCMC 0.08 mM.

temperature, which leads to molecular agitation and friction. Thereby, resulting in uniform and smaller particles of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs obtained. The micro-strain (ϵ) was calculated using the formula¹⁴.

$$\epsilon = \frac{\beta \cos \theta}{4}$$

The observed parameters from XRD spectra were listed in Table 1. The slight shift in the XRD spectrum and the change in the d -value and the lattice constant with NaCMC capped indicated that NaCMC has really capped into ZnO lattice. The micro-strain was 1.0159×10^{-3} for sample a and 0.9743×10^{-3} for 0.08 mM. The intrinsic stress was changed monotonically with increasing the NaCMC molar ratio due to the change in the micro structure, size, and shape of the particles. The value of the dislocation density (δ) was calculated using the formula¹⁵.

$$\delta = \frac{1}{D^2}$$

Table 1. The observed parameters from XRD spectra of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs (a) NaCMC 0.04 mM, (b) NaCMC 0.08 mM

Samples	2θ values	d-space values	Cell parameter			Average crystalline size (D) nm	Micro-strain (ε) × 10 ⁻³	Dislocation (δ) × 10 ⁻⁴
			a = b	c	Ratio c/a			
ZnO/NaCMC (0.04 mM)	36.236	2.4770	2.867	5.212	1.8179	34.1	1.0159	8.650
ZnO/NaCMC (0.08 mM)	36.223	2.4779	2.866	5.212	1.8186	35.2	0.9743	8.632

The dislocation densities of the NaCMC capped ZnO NPs were found to be 8.650×10^{-4} for sample a and 8.632×10^{-4} for sample b. The decrease of lattice constants, reduction in the particle size decrease in dislocation density, the broad reflection peak and a small shift in XRD peaks confirmed the formation of the system.

Spectral analysis (FT-IR) :

The FT-IR spectra of the prepared NaCMC capped zinc oxide NPs were shown in Fig. 2. The strong characteristic absorption peak at 420 cm^{-1} indicated the formation of stretching mode of Zn-O bond¹⁶. The broad absorption peak around 3400 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} could be attributed to the characteristic absorption of hydroxyls¹⁷.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs : (a) NaCMC 0.04 mM, (b) NaCMC 0.08 mM.

Surface morphological analysis (SEM/EDS) :

The SEM micrographs of prepared NPs were as shown in Fig. 3. The SEM micrographs indicated that the samples were composed with large quantity of NPs with uniform size and shape. It clearly showed that they were distinctive outlines such as triangle, circle, rectangle and square. The NaCMC acted as a capping agent and exerted a strong influence on the shape of the particles by governing the

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs : (a) NaCMC 0.04 mM, (b) NaCMC 0.08 mM.

growth rate of various crystallographic surfaces. The EDS spectrum of NaCMC capped ZnO (0.04 mM) shown in Fig. 4. The zinc and oxygen were present in the spectrum and hence the purity of ZnO nanostructures was established.

Topographic analysis (AFM) :

The topographic image of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs (0.04 mM) was shown in Fig. 5. The root mean square (RMS) roughness of the sample was studied. The NaCMC capped ZnO NPs (0.04 mM) was around 50 nm over an area of $1 \mu\text{m}^2$. The analysis revealed that the prepared sample exhibited very smooth surface and good crystal structures. It is a characterization technique for the examination of nanomaterials in contact mode. The AFM after significant advantage of probing in high details the surface topography qualitatively (by surface image) due

Fig. 4. EDS spectrum of NaCMC capped ZnO (0.04 mM) NPs.

Fig. 5. AFM image of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs (0.04 mM).

to its nanometer scale spatial resolution, both lateral and vertical. AFM has proved to be very helpful for the determination and verification of various morphological features and parameters. The particle size of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs was estimated (35 nm) and it was in agreement with XRD analysis (34.1 nm).

Optical absorption analysis (UV-Vis) :

UV absorption spectroscopy is a powerful non-destructive test to explore the optical properties of prepared NPs. The absorption spectra of samples in UV-Visible range were shown in Fig. 6. The absorption spectra showed a significant blue shift compared to that the bulk zinc oxide. From the figure, absorption around 270 nm due to relatively large exciton binding energy of prepared particles. The prepared samples were excellent in UV absorption. The intensity of absorbance reduced when decrease size of the NPs, size of the NaCMC capped ZnO

NPs (0.04 mM) was 34.1 nm from Table 1. The NaCMC acted as an excellent capping agent during the formation of ZnO NPs. The energy band gap (E_g) was calculated for the synthesized NaCMC capped ZnO NPs (0.04 mM and 0.08 mM) were 3.5 eV and 3.52 eV respectively.

Photo degradation analysis :

The decomposition effect of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs was observed against methylene orange dye in the presence of sun light. The sun light was absorbed by ZnO NPs promoted the electrons from valence band (VB) to conduction band (CB).

The photo generated holes reacted with water and formed hydroxyl radical. The hydroxyl radicals were the most potent oxidizing agents. The degradation rate confirmed the potency of the hydroxyl radical. The photo generated electrons reacted with molecular oxygen and produced superoxide radical anions. These reactive radicals are

Fig. 6. UV-Vis spectra of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs : (a) NaCMC 0.04 mM, (b) NaCMC 0.08 mM.

responsible for the degradation of methylene orange dye solution.

The UV-Vis absorption spectra of methylene orange (MO) solution in the presence of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs with irradiation of sun light for different time intervals were shown in Fig. 7. The prepared NaCMC capped ZnO NPs (0.04 mM) showed good degradation effect. The photo degradation spectrum was drawn between absorption intensity and sun light irradiation time¹⁸.

$$D (\%) = \frac{A_0 - A_t}{A_0} \times 100$$

where, D is the degradation efficiency (in %). A_0 is the UV absorption of dye with sun light irradiation time (0 min) and A_t is the UV absorption of dye after sun light irradiation (t -min). These results confirm the red-shifted in UV absorption spectrum (650–675 nm). The degradation efficiency of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs was estimated as 43%. This process could be suitable to treat the contamination from river water¹⁹.

Fig. 7. UV-Vis absorption spectra of MO solution in the presence of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs (0.04 mM) with irradiation of sun light for different time intervals.

Conclusion

In present investigation, pure and NaCMC capped ZnO NPs with different molar concentration (0.04 mM and 0.08 mM). The XRD analysis showed that the samples were hexagonal wurtzite structure. The particle size of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs with molar concentration 0.04 mM was 34.1 nm. The FTIR studies confirmed presence of the functional groups for ZnO NPs. The ZnO NPs appeared to be bigger and more crystalline in SEM micrograph analysis. The EDS spectrum of NaCMC capped ZnO (0.04 mM) established the purity of ZnO NPs. The particle size of NaCMC capped ZnO NPs (0.04 mM) calculated using AFM analysis (35 nm) which in agreement with XRD analysis. The energy band gap (E_g) of the synthesized NaCMC capped ZnO NPs in different molar ratio of (0.04 mM and 0.08 mM) were 3.5 eV and 3.52 eV respectively by UV-Vis analysis. The photo degradation efficiency percentage was calculated for NaCMC capped ZnO NPs with different irradiation time. The maximum 43% photo degradation efficiency was estimated for 150 min sun light irradiation time in the MO solution. The prepared NaCMC ZnO NPs were the potential candidates for photo degradation process.

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